

GEOPOLYMERIC PRODUCTS SYNTHESIZED IN THE LABORATORY

Università
di Catania

Mortars for repair and finishing interventions on masonry

- Fly ash/metakaolin based mortars (one part/two parts methods)
 - Na-based alkali activators
 - K-based alkali activators

36 formulations

Additives: lime/slaked lime; **aggregates:** grinded basalts/*cocciopesto*/sand

Consolidants for the restoration of deteriorated masonry

- Fly ash/metakaolin based mortars
 - Na-based alkali activators
 - K-based alkali activators

30 formulations

Additives: slaked lime/Xanthan gum

Mosaic tesserae (pigmented) for replacement interventions of compromised original elements

- Fly ash/metakaolin based mortars (one part/two parts methods)
 - Na-based alkali activators
 - K-based alkali activators

6 formulations

Tiles for replacement interventions of compromised original elements (glazed and un-glazed)

- Pre-casted elements
 - Ceramic wastes based

3 formulations

**PATENT
PENDING**

Products characterization:

- X-Ray Diffraction (XRD)
- X-Ray Fluorescence (XRF)
- Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR)
- Mechanical strength
- Morphological analyses (SEM-EDS)
- Rheological Test
- Vicat test